

Synthesis, reactions and characterization of seven-coordinate lanthanide (Ln) tetraisopropoxoaluminate complexes $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]$

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Abstract : The 1 : 2 reactions between $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ and $\text{K}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ in benzene-isopropyl alcohol, afford novel heptacoordinate lanthanide complexes of the type $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]$, where Ln = La (1), Nd (2), Gd (3), Ho (4), Yb (5) and Lu (6). Reactions of some of these complexes with an excess of tetrahydrofuran (THF) or pyridine (Py), produce complexes in which coordinated Pr^iOH is replaced by THF or Py. Heating or volatilization of seven-coordinate lanthanide(III) complexes under reduced pressure give six-coordinate complexes, $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]$. Unsolvated complexes, when Ln = La or Gd on reactions with two equivalents of KOPr^i in benzene medium yield dimeric compounds having $\text{Ln}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Ln}$ bridging unit, $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)\}_2]$. All of these new complexes have been characterized by analysis, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (when Ln = La, Nd, Lu) and IR spectroscopy and ebullioscopic molecular weight measurements.

Keywords : Heptacoordination, lanthanide complexes, tetraisopropoxoaluminates, heterobimetallic isopropoxides.

Introduction

Tetraisopropoxoaluminate is a versatile chelating ligand^{1,2}, exhibiting η^2 and/or η^3 bonding modes, but the former type is more prevalent. The synthesis and X-ray structure of a heptacoordinate praseodymium(III), isopropoxoaluminate complex³, $[\{\text{Pr}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]$ prompted us to synthesize and study chemistry of six- and seven-coordinate yttrium and lanthanide complexes of alkoxometallate ligands⁴, and we report in this paper isopropoxoaluminate complexes of both lighter and heavier lanthanides in seven- or six-coordination state and their characterization by physicochemical methods.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The reactions in 1 : 2 molar ratios of $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ with $\text{K}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ in benzene-propan-2-ol afford an interesting type of heptacoordinate lanthanide complexes (Table 1) according to the following reaction :

Ln = La (1), Nd (2), Gd (3), Ho (4), Yb (5) and Lu (6)

The unsolvated products can be obtained by the following synthetic pathway :

Ln = La (7), Nd (8), Gd (9), Ho (10), Yb (11), Lu (12)

Ligand displacement reactions :

The reactions of the complexes (1), (4), and (6) with an excess of THF and those of (1) and (6) with pyridine (Py), resulted in the displacement of coordinated Pr^iOH :

The ease of elimination (by evacuation at room temperature) of propan-2-ol follows the following order : La < Nd < Gd < Ho < Yb < Lu, which reflects the effect

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of lanthanide contraction on the stability of these higher coordinate species.

Metathetical reactions :

The dimeric chloro complexes of the type $[\{\text{Ln}(\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4)_2(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]$, react with two equivalents KOPr^i to yield new heterobimetallic derivatives :

(18) : Ln = La; (19) : Ln = Pr; (20) : Ln = Gd

All these heterobimetallic coordination compounds (Tables 1 and 2) are highly moisture-sensitive colourless or coloured solids or viscous and/or sticky products. These are soluble in benzene or toluene. The compounds are volatile under reduced pressure and depict dimeric behaviour in boiling benzene.

Table 1. Analytical and some physical data for new complexes $[\{\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}_2\text{Ln}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})\}_2]^a$

(Complex) Ln	Colour and nature yield (g, %)	Analysis (%) :				Mol. wt Found (Calcd.)
		Found (Calcd.)				
		Ln	Al	OPr ⁱ	Cl	
(1) La	White solid	18.2	7.0	69.6	4.6	1510
	(4.01, 99)	(18.3)	(7.1)	(69.9)	(4.7)	(1522)
(2) Nd	Blue solid	18.6	6.9	69.1	4.7	1528
	(3.47, 96)	(18.8)	(7.0)	(69.5)	(4.6)	(1534)
(3) Gd	White soft solid	20.3	6.8	68.0	4.5	1552
	(4.28, 99)	(20.2)	(6.9)	(68.4)	(4.6)	(1560)
(4) Ho	Light yellow	20.9	7.0	67.2	4.6	1568
	sticky solid (6.02, 96)	(21.0)	(6.9)	(67.7)	(4.5)	(1574)
(5) Yb	White sticky	21.7	6.9	66.6	4.6	1585
	solid (3.53, 99)	(21.8)	(6.8)	(67.0)	(4.5)	(1590)
(6) Lu	White solid	21.6	6.7	66.3	4.6	1588
	(4.22, 98)	(21.9)	(6.8)	(66.8)	(4.5)	(1594)

^aRecrystallization from $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$ at -20°C afford product of identical composition in 70–80% yield.

Table 2. Analytical and some physical data for complexes (7)–(12) $[\{\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}_2\text{Ln}(\mu\text{-Cl})\}_2]^a$

(Complex) Ln	Colour and nature	Volatility (°C/mm)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mol. wt Found (Calcd.)
			Ln	Al	OPr ⁱ	Cl	
(7) La	White solid	205/0.2	19.9	7.6	67.2	5.0	1396
			(19.8)	(7.7)	(67.4)	(5.1)	(1402)
(8) Nd	Blue solid	207/0.01	20.3	7.6	66.5	5.1	1402
			(20.4)	(7.6)	(66.9)	(5.0)	(1412)

Infrared spectral studies :

Infrared spectra of (1)–(20) exhibit structurally important absorptions^{4,5} (in cm^{-1}) at 1370–1365 and 1360–1355 $[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}, \text{C-H deformation}]$, 1125–1110 and 1160–1150 (skeletal vibrations of *gem*-dimethyl group), 1030–1000 $[\nu(\text{C-O}) \text{ terminal}]$, 995–930 $[\nu(\text{C-O}) \text{ bridging}]$, 705–670 $\nu(\text{Al-O})$, 455–400 $\nu(\text{Ln-O})$ and 250–200 $\nu(\text{Ln-Cl})$.

A broad and strong band observed at $\sim 3080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes (1–6) has been assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$. In parent alcohol this band appears at $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the lowering can be explained to arise from the coordination of Pr^iOH molecule to the central lanthanide atom^{5b}.

The C–O–C vibrational mode, observed at 1070 cm^{-1} in the free THF molecules shifted to lower frequencies by $\sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes (13)–(15) indicating coordination through the oxygen atom⁶ of the THF molecule.

The $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ mode of the free pyridine at 1578 cm^{-1} shifted to higher frequencies by $\sim 22 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes (16)–(17). This is characteristic of coordination through nitrogen in pyridine complexes⁷. The absorptions occurring at about 320 cm^{-1} can be attributed to metal-pyridine stretching vibrations⁸.

NMR spectral studies :

(a) ¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectral studies are mainly restricted to the diamagnetic (La^{3+} and Lu^{3+}) complexes.

The spectra of (1), (2), (6), (7), (8), (12), (13), (15), (16) and (17) exhibit a doublet in the region δ 1.23–1.29 and a multiplet centred in the region δ 4.03–4.30 due to methyl and methine protons of isopropoxy groups, respectively.

In addition to the above mentioned resonances, the complexes (1), (2) and (6) show a broad peak at δ 2.27–3.40 due to the hydroxyl proton of the coordinated isopropyl alcohol^{4c}. The proton resonances due to coordi-

Table-2 (contd.)

(9) Gd	White solid	212–215/0.4	22.0 (21.9)	7.6 (7.5)	65.4 (65.7)	4.8 (4.9)	1430 (1438)
(10) Ho	Light yellow soft solid	225/0.5	22.6 (22.7)	7.5 (7.4)	64.8 (65.0)	5.0 (4.9)	1448 (1454)
(11) Yb	White soft solid	210/0.4	23.6 (23.5)	7.4 (7.3)	64.0 (64.3)	4.9 (4.8)	1466 (1470)
(12) Lu	White solid	215/0.5	23.8 (23.7)	7.2 (7.3)	64.1 (64.1)	4.9 (4.8)	1468 (1474)

^aObtained either by heating at 60–70 °C/0.9 mm or by distillation under reduced pressure, the solvated complexes of the type $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{L})\}_2]$ (L = PrⁱOH, THF or Py).

nated THF in complexes (13) and (15) have been observed^{6,9} in the regions δ 1.80–1.83 ($\beta\text{-CH}_2$) and 3.60–3.69 ($\alpha\text{-CH}_2$), while resonances due to coordinates pyridine (Py)^{4c} in (16) and (17) have been observed at δ 7.16, 7.63, and 8.66 ppm.

(b) ¹³C NMR spectral studies :

The complexes (1), (7), (12), and (16) showed signals in the regions (δ , ppm) : 25.35–28.30 (OCHMe₂) and 65.02–68.36 (OCHMe₂), respectively due to α - and β -carbon atoms of the metal-attached isopropoxo groups. The complex (16) also showed signals characteristic of coordinated pyridine moieties at 123.96, 136.42 and 150.44 ppm.

(c) ²⁷Al NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) :

²⁷Al NMR spectra of the derivatives (1), (6), (7), (12), (13), (15) and (16) exhibit broad absorptions characteristic of tetrahedral aluminium species^{4a,c,10} at δ 68.29, 73.48, 50.87, 46.66, 47.10, 60.58, and 53.06.

A perusal of electronic spectral data (see Experimental section) and shape of the hypersensitive bands and their comparisons with those already reported in the literature for seven^{4a}- and six¹¹-coordinate heterometallic-isopropoxides of lanthanide(III), indicate that the lanthanide(III) ions in complexes (2), (4) and (14) are seven-coordinate, whereas complexes (8) and (10) are six-coordinate. The positive values of $b^{1/2}$, and δ as well as less than one value of β suggest considerable covalent character in metal-ligand bond.

Comments on structural features :

The structural formulation for seven-coordinate lanthanide complexes (1)–(6) and (13)–(17) as $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{L})\}_2]$ (L = PrⁱOH, THF or Py) involv-

ing chloro-bridged dimeric structure, wherein each lanthanide atom is bidentedly bonded with two $\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}^-$ groups and coordinated with one molecule of PrⁱOH, THF, or Py, is based on X-ray crystallographically determined structure of $[\{\text{Pr}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})\}_2]$. The structural formulation of (7)–(12) and (18)–(20) as six-coordinate lanthanide(III), $[\{\text{Ln}[\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2(\mu\text{-X})\}_2]$ (X = Cl or OPrⁱ) is supported by their dimeric nature and already well established bidentate ligating mode^{3,12} of $\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}^-$.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Anhydrous lanthanide trichlorides¹³, LnCl₃·3PrⁱOH^{4a}, aluminiumisopropoxide^{5b}, and $[\{\text{Pr}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2\text{Cl}\}_2]^3$ were prepared by literature methods. The solvents : THF, benzene, toluene, *n*-hexane, pyridine and dichloromethane were refluxed over appropriate drying agents and distilled prior to use. All operations were carried out under strict moisture-free environment similar to those previously described^{4a-c}.

Measurement : Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene with a Gallenkamp-bullimeter using a thermister sensing device. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : Infrared spectra (4000–200 cm⁻¹) were recorded as Nujol mulls on Perkin-Elmer 557 and Carl Zeiss Specord M80 spectrophotometers using CsI optics; ¹H (89.55 MHz) and ¹³C (22.49 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃; ²⁷Al (23.29 MHz) spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ or C₆H₆ and referenced to $[\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (external); UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicame Model SP 8-100 spectrophotometer in benzene.

Electronic spectral studies :

Hypersensitive electronic absorptions, their oscillator strengths ($P \times 10^6$), and covalency parameters : nephelauxetic^{12a} (β), bonding^{12b} ($b^{1/2}$), and percentage covalency^{12c} (δ) for Nd^{III} and Ho^{III} complexes are given below :

(2) : λ_{\max} (nm), 584 (ϵ_{\max} 19.3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 64.02 (for aqua-ions, 13.49); $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^2G_{7/2}$, $^4G_{5/2}$; β , 0.990, δ , 0.967; $b^{1/2}$, 0.044.

(4) : λ_{\max} (nm), 360 (ϵ_{\max} 6.76 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 5.60 (for aqua-ions, 3.11); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^3H_6$; λ_{\max} (nm), 452 (ϵ_{\max} 6.02 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 12.46 (for aqua-ions, 8.66); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^5G_6$, 5F_1 ; β , 0.9934, δ , 0.668; $b^{1/2}$, 0.039.

(8) : λ_{\max} (nm), 590 (ϵ_{\max} 8.09 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 43.54 (for aqua-ions, 13.49); $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^2G_{7/2}$, $^4G_{5/2}$; β , 0.9805, δ , 2.00; $b^{1/2}$, 0.066.

(10) : λ_{\max} (nm), 368 (ϵ_{\max} 6.79 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 16.87 (for aqua-ions, 3.11); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^3H_6$; λ_{\max} (nm), 458 (ϵ_{\max} 8.70 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 21.16 (for aqua-ions, 8.66); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^5G_6$, 5F_1 ; β , 0.9843; δ , 1.79; $b^{1/2}$, 0.064.

(14) : λ_{\max} (nm), 364 (ϵ_{\max} 6.60 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 6.56 (for aqua-ions, 3.11); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^3H_6$; λ_{\max} (nm), 455 (ϵ_{\max} 7.39 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); $P \times 10^6$, 25.87 (for aqua-ions, 8.66); $^5I_8 \rightarrow ^5G_6$, 5F_1 ; β , 0.9892; δ , 1.095; $b^{1/2}$, 0.051.

Lanthanides (Ln) were estimated by complexometric titrations with EDTA^{4c} using xylenol orange as indicator. Aluminium was estimated by the oxinate method¹⁴. Isopropoxy contents were estimated by the oxidimetric method¹⁵ using N-K₂Cr₂O₇ solution in 12.5% H₂SO₄. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method¹⁴.

Preparation of complexes :

Analytical data for the new complexes are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Synthesis of [$\{Nd[\eta^2-Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(Pr^iOH)(\mu-Cl)\}_2$] (2) :

A solution of K{Al(OPrⁱ)₄} [freshly prepared by the reaction of potassium (0.37 g, 9.46 mg atom) with isopropyl alcohol (~10 ml), followed by the addition of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ (1.94 g, 9.50 mmol) and refluxing the reaction mixture for 1 h] was added slowly to a prestirred suspension of NdCl₃.3PrⁱOH (2.05 g, 4.76 mmol) in benzene

(~20 ml) and then allowed to stir at ~60 °C for ~10 h. After separation of precipitated KCl by filtration and the removal of volatiles from the filtrate under reduced pressure (30 °C/1.0 mm) afforded the title compound (3.47 g, 96%) as a blue solid. Recrystallization from CH₂Cl₂-*n*-hexane the product was obtained in 80% yield.

Adopting a similar procedure analogous complexes of other lanthanides such as La (1), Gd (3), Ho (4), Yb (5), and Lu (6) have also been synthesized. Analytical data and physical characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Reaction of [$\{[\eta^2-Al(OPr^i)_4]_2Ho(\mu-Cl)(Pr^iOH)\}_2$] (4) with an excess of tetrahydrofuran (THF) :

To a benzene (20 ml) of (4) (2.89 g, 3.67 mmol), THF (5 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at ~60 °C for 5 h. Removal of volatiles under reduced pressure (20 °C/1 mm) resulted in the analytically pure product of composition [$\{ClHo[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(THF)\}_2$] as a light yellow soft solid (2.90 g, 99%) (Found : Ho, 20.7; Al, 6.6; OPrⁱ, 59.0; Cl, 4.5. Calcd. for [$\{ClHo[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(THF)_2$] (14) : Ho, 20.6; Al, 6.7; OPrⁱ, 59.1; Cl, 4.4%).

Adopting the procedure, similar to, as described above analogous complexes of lanthanum (13) and lutetium (15) have also been prepared.

(13) (White solid) : Yield 98% (Found : La, 18.1; Al, 6.9; OPrⁱ, 61.0; Cl, 4.5. Calcd. for [$\{ClLa[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(THF)\}_2$] : La, 18.0; Al, 7.0; OPrⁱ, 61.1; Cl, 4.5%).

(15) (White solid) : Yield 99% (Found : Lu, 21.5; Al, 6.5; OPrⁱ, 58.1; Cl, 4.3. Calcd. for [$\{ClLu[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(THF)\}_2$] : Lu, 21.6; Al, 6.7; OPrⁱ, 58.4; Cl, 4.4%).

Reaction of [$\{ClLu[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(Pr^iOH)\}_2$] (6) with an excess of pyridine (Py) :

After addition of pyridine (1 ml) to a benzene (15 ml) solution of (6) (1.25 g, 1.57 mmol), the reaction mixture was stirred at ~60 °C for 10 h, distillation under reduced pressure at room temperature, afforded white solid product of composition [$\{ClLu[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(Py)\}_2$] (17). Yield (1.2 g, 99%) (Found : Lu, 21.5; Al, 6.6; OPrⁱ, 57.5; Cl, 4.4. Calcd. for (17) : Lu, 21.4; Al, 6.6; OPrⁱ, 57.9; Cl, 4.3%).

The analogous complex of lanthanum (16) was prepared in a similar manner.

(16) (White solid) : Yield (3.13 g, 98%) (Found : La, 17.9; Al, 6.9; OPrⁱ, 60.1; Cl, 4.6. Calcd. for

$[\{ClLa[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2(Py)\}_2]$: La, 17.8; Al, 6.9; OPrⁱ, 60.6; Cl, 4.5%).

Reaction of $[\{ClPr[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}_2]$ with two equivalents of KOPrⁱ :

A benzene (15 ml) suspension of KOPrⁱ [prepared by dissolving potassium (0.16 g, 4.09 mg atom) in isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) and benzene (10 ml) followed by the removal of volatiles under reduced pressure] was added to a solution of $[\{ClPr[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}_2]$ (2.85 g, 2.01 mmol) in benzene (25 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred at ~60 °C for 5 h. Removal of filtrate under reduced pressure yielded green solid. The compound of composition $[\{Pr^iOPr[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}]$ (**19**) was purified by distillation at 185 °C/0.1 mm in 72% yield (Found : Pr, 19.2; Al, 7.5; OPrⁱ, 72.8; M.W. 1432. Calcd. for $[\{Pr^iOPr[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}]$: Pr, 19.3; Al, 7.4%; OPrⁱ, 73.2%, M.W. 1450).

Products of similar composition of lanthanum and gadolinium have also been prepared by adopting the above procedure :

$[\{Pr^iOLa[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}_2]$ (**18**) : White solid, b.p. 170 °C/0.05 mm; yield 75% (Found : La, 19.1; Al, 7.3; OPrⁱ, 72.9; M.W. 1449. Calcd. for (**18**) : La, 19.2; Al, 7.4; OPrⁱ, 73.4%; M.W. 1448).

$[\{Pr^iOGd[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2\}_2]$ (**20**) : White solid; b.p. 180 °C/0.03 mm; yield 74% (Found : Gd, 21.0; Al, 7.2; OPrⁱ, 71.3; M.W. 1450. Calcd. for (**20**) : Gd, 21.2; Al, 7.3; OPrⁱ, 71.5%; M.W. 1459).

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References

- (a) K. G. Caulton and L. G. Hubert-Pfalzgraf, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 969; (b) U. M. Tripathi, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1287; (c) R. C. Mehrotra and J. V. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 109.
- See for example : D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic Press, London/New York, 2001.
- U. M. Tripathi, A. Singh, R. C. Mehrotra, S. C. Goel, M. Y. Chiang and W. E. Buhro, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 152.
- (a) S. Mishra, U. M. Tripathi, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 689 and references cited therein; (b) S. Mishra, U. M. Tripathi and A. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 801 and references cited therein; (c) U. M. Tripathi, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 1947.
- (a) C. G. Barraclough, D. C. Bradley, J. Lewis and I. Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2601; (b) L. M. Brown and K. S. Mazdiyasi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 2783; (c) L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
- R. Gupta, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 596 and references cited therein.
- R. C. Chhipa, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 792 and references cited therein.
- (a) R. J. H. Clark and C. S. Williams, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 351; (b) D. H. Brown and P. T. Richardson, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 755.
- R. C. Chhipa, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 645.
- J. W. Akitt and Gessner, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 147.
- S. Mishra, U. M. Tripathi, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **49**, 1 and references cited therein.
- M. Wijk, R. Norrestam, M. Nygren and G. Westin, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 1077.
- J. H. Freeman and M. L. Smith, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **7**, 224.
- G. H. Jeffery, J. Bassett, J. Mendham and R. C. Denney, "Vogel's : Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., Addison Wesley Longman Inc, UK, 1989.
- R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 585.

